

The Effect of Mudharabah Financing and Musyarakah Financing on Profitability (ROE) through Profit-Sharing Income in Islamic Banks in 2015-2018

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Abstract:- This study aims to examine the effect of mudharabah and musyarakah financing on the profitability of Islamic banks through profit sharing. The approach used in this research is a quantitative approach. The samples used in this study were 9 Islamic banks during the 2015-2018 research period. Research data were analyzed using path analysis techniques with the help of the Smartpls program. The results of this study indicate that (1) Mudharabah financing has a positive and significant effect on profit sharing, meaning that the higher the mudharabah financing, the higher the profit sharing income for Islamic banks, and vice versa, mudharabah financing which is easy has the potential to reduce profit sharing income for Islamic banks; (2) Musyarakah financing has no effect on profit sharing, this means that the level of musyarakah financing has no effect on the level of profit sharing income of Islamic banks; (3) Mudharabah financing has a positive and significant effect on ROE, meaning that the higher the mudharabah financing, the higher the ROE value of the bank, and vice versa the lower the mudharabah financing, the lower the ROE value of Islamic banks; (4) Musyarakah income has a negative and significant effect on ROE, meaning that the higher the musyarakah financing, the lower the Islamic bank's ROE value, and vice versa the lower the musyarakah financing, the higher the Islamic bank's ROE; (5) Profit sharing income does not affect the profitability of Islamic banks, the level of profit sharing income does not significantly affect the ROE of Islamic banks; (6) Revenue sharing does not compensate for the effect of mudharabah financing on profitability and (7) Revenue sharing does not compensate for the effect of musyarakah financing on profitability.

Keywords:- mudharabah financing, musyarakah financing, profitability, profit sharing.

I. INTRODUCTION

According to banking law number 10 of 1998, a bank is a business entity that collects public funds in the form of deposits and distributes them to the public in the form of credit and or other forms in order to improve people's living standards. As a financial institution, the bank has funding and financing activities or collecting and distributing funds. So as a medium for connecting banks, they act as intermediaries between parties who have excess funds and parties who need financial assistance.

Banks in Indonesia are divided into two groups, namely banks based on conventional principles, the majority of banks that develop in Indonesia are banks oriented towards conventional principles. Banks based on Sharia principles, namely banks based on Islamic Sharia principles that have recently developed in Indonesia.

According to Rachmadi Usman, "A Sharia bank or Islamic bank is a business entity whose function is to collect funds from the community and distribute funds to the community, whose system and mechanism of business activities are based on Islamic law as regulated in the Qur'an and Al Hadith. Islamic banks have products or services that will not be found in conventional bank operations. Principles such as musyarakah, mudharabah, murabahah, ijarah, istishna, and so on do not contain the existence of interest principles such as those developed by conventional banks. Therefore, Sharia Banks are experiencing increasingly rapid development, this can be seen from the many branches of Sharia Banks in Indonesia.

The Islamic banking products that are the focus of this study and affect the profit achieved are through mudharabah financing and musyarakah financing.

To Create harmony between that growth and equity, it needs institutions that control and regulate the dynamics of the economy in this case the turnover of money and goods. That function actually brings many benefits, because it meets owners, users, and capital managers. Basically, Islamic banks, like conventional banks, also distribute funds to the public in the form of credit or financing, it's just that there are fundamental differences in terms of rewards. The determination of the desired and future rewards given by

Islamic banks to their customers is based solely on the profit-sharing principle.

Each bank product provides benefits for the bank, as well as investment financing. The profit can be seen from the level of profitability measured using financial ratios. The financial ratio used is the Return On Equity ratio, which is the rate of return on capital of the bank. The reason for using the ratio is because it is to find out the ability of bank to manage its capital for mudharabah and musyarakah financing. This ratio is also a measure of the joint ownership of the owners of such banks.

In accordance with the concept of profitability, one of the things that affect the profitability of a bank is the financing channeled by a bank. If the level of financing is high, then profitability will increase. Profitability can be interpreted as one of the indicators to measure the performance of a company (Harahap, 2008: 297). The calculation that will be used in this study is Return On Equity (ROE) which is a comparison between net profit after tax and own capital.

Profitability is one of the bank analysis tools used to assess management's performance in making a profit or profit from the business operations of a bank. High profitability can indicate good financial performance of the bank. On the other hand, if the profitability achieved is low, it indicates a lack of maximum financial performance in making a profit. If low profitability continues to be allowed, it will have an impact on the low image of the bank in the eyes of the public to decline. With a decrease in public trust, it can cause the process of raising funds to be problematic.

II. MATERIALS AND METODHS

A. Islamic Banks in Islam

Philosophically, Islamic banks are banks whose activities leave usury problems behind (Machmud, 2010: 4). Islamic banks are financial institutions whose main business is to provide financing and other services in payment traffic and money circulation and whose operation is in accordance with Islamic principles. Meanwhile, banks that operate according to Islamic sharia principles are banks that in their operation follow the provisions of Islamic Sharia (Muhammad, 2004: 1). Meanwhile, a bank that operates in accordance with Islamic Sharia principles is a bank that in its operation follows the provisions of Islamic Sharia, especially those concerning procedures for Islamicmuamalat. It further said that in the ordinance of charity, it is shunned the practices - practices that are feared to contain elements of usury to be filled with investment activities on the basis of profit sharing and trade finance. The main principles followed by Islamic banks are:

- Prohibition of usury in various forms of transactions.
- Conducting business and trading activities based on legitimate profit.
- Giving zakat.

B. Sharia Bank Products

Ascarya, 2011, Islamic bank products are divided into four, namely:

- Funding products that include entrustment patterns (wadiyah) in the form of current accounts and savings, loans (qardh) in the form of current accounts and savings, profit sharing (mudharabah) in the form of savings, deposits and bonds and rent (ijarah) in the form of bonds.
- Financing products include profit sharing patterns (mudharabah and musyarakah) in the form of investment and working capital financing, buying and selling (murabahah, salam, isthisna) in the form of property financing, leases (ijarah) in the form of leases and asset acquisitions and loans (qardh) in the form of securities financing.
- Banking service products that include a entrustment pattern (wadiyah) in the form of a safe deposit box, profit sharing (mudharabah) in the form of bound investments and other patterns (wakalah, kafalah, hawalah, rahn, ujr, sharf) in the form of transfers and clearing.
- Social activity products in the form of loan patterns (qardh) applied to bailouts to customers and donations in the small business sector.

C. Mudharabah Financing

One of the main activities of Islamic banks is to channel their excess funds in the form of financing. In Islamic banks, financing is a banking product based on the principles of Islamic teachings and is not only oriented toward bank profits but is expected to provide benefits for customers who partner with Islamic banks. The objectives of this financing are:

- Macro-wise is an increase in the economy, the availability of funds for business improvement, increasing productivity, creating new jobs, and income distribution.
- Macro-wise, it is an effort to maximize profits, efforts to minimize risks, utilize economic resources, and distribute excess funds. (Muhammad in Sari,2013:35)

By the nature of its use, this financing is divided into two, namely:

- Productive financing, to meet the financing of production needs.
- Consumptive financing, to meet consumption needs.

So, this mudharabah financing is an investment transaction in the context of providing business capital for a certain period of time in accordance with the mutual agreement between the bank and the customer. There are various types of Islamic banking products and financial institutions based on the concept of mudharabah. However, in general, mudharabah financing in Islamic banking can be categorized into two major parts, namely:

- **MudharabahMutlaqah**, i.e. mudharib is given full power to manage capital. Mudharib is not restricted either regarding the place, destination or type of business.
- **MudharabahMuqayyadah**, i.e. shahibulmaal sets certain conditions that mudharib must comply with both regarding the place, purpose, and type of business. In this system, mudharabah is not allowed to mix with other capital or funds.

D. Musyarakah Financing

Al-Musyarakah is a business cooperation agreement between two or more parties in running a business, where each party includes its capital in accordance with the agreement, and profit sharing or joint efforts are given in accordance with the contribution of funds or according to mutual agreement. Musyarakah, also known as syirkah, is an activity of association in carrying out joint efforts between related parties.

There are 2 types of musyarakah financing, namely:

- Syirkah Al-Milk, ownership of two or more parties of a property.
- Syirkah Al-'Aqd, a partnership occurs because of a joint contract. Syirkah Al-'Aqd' is divided into four, namely:
 - ✓ Syirkah Al-Amwal, cooperation between business partners where the portion of capital participation and cooperation is not the same.
 - ✓ Syirkah Al-Mufawadhah, cooperation between business partners with the same portion of capital participation, profit sharing and work management.
 - ✓ Syirkah Al-A'mal, a cooperation where all business partners participate in providing services to customers.
 - ✓ Syirkah Al-Wujuh, cooperation in which mitra business has no investment at all. (Ascarya,2011:49)

E. ROE (Return Of Equity) Profitability

In general, the profitability ratios that are often used by banks to determine their financial performance return on assets (ROA) and return on equity (ROE). ROA is a ratio to assess how much a bank's ability to manage assets to generate net profit, while ROE is a ratio to see how much a bank's ability to manage capital to generate a net profit.

ROE is defined as a comparison between net income and average equity or investment by bank owners. From the view of the owners, ROE is a more important measure because it reflects their interests. For bank owners, it is a result of the level of profit from the asset and the level of leverage used.

The formula in calculating ROE is:

$$ROE = \frac{Net\ Income}{Equity\ Income} \times 100\%$$

Fig. 1: Formula of ROE

Based on this frame of mind, the model framework in this study is as follows:

Fig. 2: Flowchart Variables

III. RESEARCH METHODS

A. Research Object

The object of research is an Islamic bank listed on the IDX in 2015-2018. The object of this study is mudharabah financing, musyarakah financing, profitability through profit sharing income. This research was conducted by the Islamic Banking Industry which was listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) for the 2015-2018 period. The population was recorded until 2018 at 9 banks.

B. Measurement of Research Variables

The analysis stage in this study includes several stages, namely (1) the Descriptive Analysis Stage and (2) the Path Analysis Stage with SmartPLS which is used to test hypotheses in this study.

➤ **Analysis of Educational Research Variables**

In this study, a descriptive analysis of respondents' characteristics was carried out by creating a frequency distribution table that showed the percentage of respondents based on their characteristics. A frequency distribution table was obtained from descriptive analysis treated with the help of the SPSS version 25 program. The characteristics of the respondents analyzed in this study were musyarakah financing, mudharabah financing, and profitability (ROE).

➤ **Path Analysis**

Hypothesis testing in this study was carried out using path analysis techniques with the help of the Smartpls program. Based on the model framework in this study, the path diagram that will be identified in this study is as follows:

Fig. 3: PLS Spesification Model

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Development of Models Based on Theory

In this study, there are four variables that will be analyzed. Where these variables are independent variables, namely mudharabah financing, musyarakah financing, and profitability as dependent variables and profit sharing income as intervening variables

B. Hypothesis Test

➤ **Descriptive Statistics**

	Median	Min	Max	Mean	SD
Mudharabah	26.024	18.092	29.146	24.79	2.877
Musyarakah	27.769	20.303	30.671	27.626	3.212
Bagi Hasil	26.966	20.23	29.236	26.333	2.478
ROE	0.028	-0.069	0.12	0.028	0.032

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

➤ **Fit Goodness Test**

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Bagi hasil	0.563	0.521
ROE	0.813	0.785

Table 2: Fit Goodness Test

Q Square indicates a predictive relevance model, where Q Square values of 0.02 – 0.15 indicate that the model has a small predictive relevance, Q Square of 0.15 – 0.35 indicates that the model has moderate predictive relevance and Q square > 0.35 indicates a large predictive relevance model (Chin, 1998). The results of the analysis in Table 4.16 show that Q Square's revenue share and ROE are in the big category.

	SSO	SSE	Q² (=1-SSE/SSO)
Bagi hasil	24.000	11.636	0.515
Mudharabah	24.000	24.000	
Musyarakah	24.000	24.000	
ROE	24.000	5.950	0.752

Table 3: Q Square Model

In addition to being judged from the value of R square and Q Square, the goodness of fit of the model is also seen from the SRMR value of the model, the model is declared perfect fit if the SRMR of the model is <0.08 and the model is declared fit if the SRMR value of the model is between 0.08 – 0.10. The results of the analysis in the table above show that the model's SRMR value is in the perfect fit category.

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.000	0.000
d ULS	0.000	0.000
d G	0.000	0.000
Chi-Square	0.000	0.000
NFI	1.000	1.000

Table 4: SRMR Model

➤ *Intervariable Influence Testing*

Fig. 4: Result of Estimate Bootstrapping Model

Based on the test results, it can be seen that the Tolerance value of all tolerance values of the variable shows greater than 0.1. Meanwhile, the VIF value of NPL The VIF value of all these variables has a result smaller than 10.00. So it can be concluded that multicollinearity does not occur.

➤ *Direct Influence Test Results*

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Bagi hasil -> ROE	-0.517	1.023	0.153
Mudharabah -> Bagi hasil	0.751	1.825	0.034
Mudharabah -> ROE	2.037	4.123	0.000
Musyarakah -> Bagi hasil	0.001	0.001	0.500
Musyarakah -> ROE	-1.405	2.589	0.005

Table 5: Direct Influence Test Results

Based on the test results, the following results were obtained:

- **Mudharabah → Revenue Sharing**
Mudharabah has a positive and significant effect on revenue sharing, indicated by sig. = 0.034 < 0.05, t statistical 1.825 > 1.65 and a positive path coefficient of 0.751, meaning that the higher the mudharabah financing, the higher the revenue sharing income of Islamic banks, and vice versa, mudharabah financing that is rendah has the potential to reduce the profit sharing income of Islamic banks.
- **Musyarakah → Profit Sharing**
Musyarakah financing has no effect on profit sharing indicated by sig. = 0.500 > 0.05 and statistical t 0.001 < 1.65, this means that the high and low of musyarakah financing does not affect the high and low revenue sharing income of Islamic banks.
- **Mudharabah → ROE**
Mudharabah has a positive and significant effect on ROE, indicated by sig. = 0.000 < 0.05, t statistic 4.123 > 1.65 and a positive path coefficient of 2.037, meaning that the higher the mudharabah financing, the higher the ROE

value of the bank, and vice versa, the lower the mudharabah financing, the lower the ROE value of Islamic banks.

- **Musyarakah → ROE**
Musyarakah income has a negative and significant effect on ROE, indicated by sig. = 0.005 < 0.05, T statistical 2.589 > 1.65 and a negative path coefficient of -1.405, meaning that the higher the musyarakah financing, the lower the ROE value of Islamic banks, and vice versa, the lower the musyarakah financing, the higher the ROE value of Islamic banks.
- **Revenue Share → ROE**
Revenue sharing has no effect on roe indicated by sig. = 0.153 > revenue sharing income has no effect on high low ROE

V. **INDIRECT INFLUENCE TEST RESULTS**

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Mudharabah -> Bagi_hasil -> ROE	-0.388	1.006	0.157
Musyarakah -> Bagi_hasil -> ROE	0.001	0.000	0.500

Table 6: Result of Indirect Effect

Based on the test results, the following results were obtained:

- **Mudharabah Line → Revenue Sharing → ROE**
In the indirect path of the effect of mudharabah financing on ROE through revenue sharing, a p-value of 0.157 was obtained with a statistical T of 1.006, because the p-value obtained > 0.05 and statistical T < 1.96, it was concluded that mudharabah financing cannot have an indirect effect on ROE by mediated by revenue sharing. In this PLS model, revenue sharing is proven to be not a mediator of the indirect influence of mudharabah financing on ROE.

- Musyarakah Path → Revenue Sharing → ROE
 In the indirect path of the effect of musyarakah financing on ROE through profit-sharing income, a p-value of 0.500 is obtained with a statistical T of 0.000, because the p-value obtained > 0.05 and the statistical T < 1.96, it is concluded that musyarakah financing cannot have an

indirect effect on ROE by being mediated by profit sharing income. In this PLS model, profit-sharing financing is proven to be not a mediator of the indirect influence of revenue on ROE.

C. Interpretation of results

No	Hipotesis	Koefisien Jalur	P Values
1	Pembiayaan Mudharabah berpengaruh positif terhadap pendapatan bagi hasil	0,751 **	Diterima
2	Pembiayaan Musyarakah berpengaruh positif terhadap pendapatan bagi hasil	0,001	Tidak diterima
3	Pembiayaan Mudharabah berpengaruh positif terhadap ROE	2,037***	Diterima
4	Pembiayaan Musyarakah berpengaruh positif terhadap ROE	-0,1405***	Diterima
5	Pendapatan bagi hasil berpengaruh positif terhadap ROE	-0,517	Tidak diterima
6	Pembiayaan Mudharabah berpengaruh positif terhadap ROE melalui pendapatan bagi hasil	-0,388	Tidak diterima
7	Pembiayaan Musyarakah berpengaruh positif terhadap ROE melalui pendapatan bagi hasil	0,001	Tidak diterima

Table 7: Result of Hypothesis

Hypothesis testing in this study is based on the results of path analysis. Based on the overall results of the path analysis in this study, the following is a summary of the hypothesis testing results in this study:

- *The effect of mudharabah financing on revenue-sharing income*

The results of this study have succeeded in proving that mudharabah financing has a positive and significant effect on profit-sharing income, meaning that the higher the mudharabah financing, the higher the revenue-sharing income of Islamic banks, and vice versa, mudharabah financing has the potential to reduce the profit-sharing income of Islamic banks.

- *The Effect of Musyarakah Financing on Profit Sharing*

The results of this study prove that musyarakah financing does not affect profit-sharing income which means that the high and low level of musyarakah financing does not affect the high and low revenue-sharing income of Islamic banks.

- *Effect of Mudharabah financing on profitability (ROE)*

Hasil this study has succeeded in proving that mudharabah financing has a positive and significant effect on ROE, meaning that the higher the mudharabah financing, the higher the ROE value of the bank, and vice versa, the lower the mudharabah financing, the lower the ROE value of Islamic banks.

- *The effect of musyarakah income on the company's profitability (ROE)*

The results of this study prove that musyarakah income has a negative and significant effect on ROE, meaning that the higher the musyarakah financing, the lower the ROE value of Islamic banks, and vice versa, the lower the musyarakah financing, the higher the ROE value of Islamic banks. This negative influence is due to the risk of Musyarakah financing in the event of a loss will have an impact on the return on capital, thus affecting the decrease in the Return On Equity (ROE) rate of Islamic banks. This negative influence can also be caused because Islamic banks do not provide large dividends to capital owners/shareholders so the Return On Equity (ROE) decreases. The distribution of dividends that are not large can be caused by banks in order to improve the capital structure of Islamic banks.

- *Effect of Revenue Share Income on ROE*

The results of this study did not succeed in proving that profit-sharing income affects ROE, the results of this study show that profit-sharing income does not affect the high or low ROE of Islamic banks. The profitability of Islamic banks assessed from ROE is more influenced by mudharabah and musyarakah financing while profit-sharing income is not a factor that can significantly affect the company's profitability.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

From the results of effect mudharabah financing, musyarakah financing, and profitability through the distribution of proceeds years 2015-2018, the following conclusion can be drawn: mudharabah financing variables have a positive effect on ROE/profitability and profit sharing. Meanwhile, musyarakah financing has a positive effect on ROE/profitability but does not affect profit sharing. Re Revenue-sharing n come has no effect on profitability. And profit sharing has no effect as a variable moderation of mudharabah financing, musyarakah financing on profitability.

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